

INTERVIEW INSTRUMENT

A. Overview

The interview (60 minutes) consists of 3 main parts:

- 1) Introduction and questions about the professional context of the interviewee (maximum 20 minutes)
- 2) Discussion of requirements and rationales for judging them as security requirements or not (maximum 30 minutes)
- 3) Closing (maximum 10 minutes)

Some other important points about the setup:

- Each interview involves three persons: Interviewer (first author), Observer (second author), and Interviewee.
- The meetings are held via Zoom or Teams.
- The audio of the interviews is recorded.
- The Observer keeps track of the answers in a form shown on the screen during the interview for real-time validation by the interviewee.

B. Procedure

We follow the following procedure when performing the interviews:

- 1) Interviewer introduces purpose of study and purpose of interview (max. 5 min.), this is also done to alleviate threats to validity due to misalignment between interviewer and interviewee.
- 2) Interviewer asks permission for recording and, when obtained, observer starts audio recording. In parallel, observer is taking notes and is ready to step in with follow-up questions in case some answers required clarification.
- 3) The observer shares the screen with the questionnaire open. During the interview, the observer will keep track of the answers of the interviewee and summarize them in the form. In that way, the interviewee can already during the interview validate that their answers are recorded correctly.
- 4) To start the interview itself, the interviewer asks simple context questions first:
 - a) What is your job title/position?
 - b) How many years of work experience do you have in total in similar roles?
 - c) Approximately, how many employees are working in your company?
 - d) Approximately, how many employees are working in your team?
- 5) We then ask about the role of the person in their company and the responsibilities in their position with respect to security and security requirements. We limit this part of the interview to a maximum of 10 minutes.

Questions to be answered:

- a) What are your responsibilities with respect to security?
- b) What are your responsibilities with respect to requirements?
- c) What security aspects do you work with?

- d) Do you write/ elicit/ review/ manage requirements?
- e) Who writes the requirements in your team/ project/ company?

6) We then start to “play the game”, and while there is time left and there are requirements left out of our prepared set of requirements, we do the following:

- a) Interviewer introduces the next requirement
- b) Interviewer asks interviewee to think aloud and to classify the requirement on a scale from “not at all a security requirement” to “absolutely a security requirement”, and answers any possible questions from interviewee to clarify the process or the requirement.
- c) Interviewer inquires about the rationale for the classification, depending on how much information they disclose, we ask these progressively more detailed further questions to understand their rationale:
 - i) Can you explain your classification?
 - ii) Did you use a specific strategy to classify this requirement, and if so, what is the strategy?
 - iii) What aspects of the requirement makes you classify the requirement as you did?
 - iv) Where there any keywords that made you classify the requirement as you did?
 - v) What security concepts (e.g., assets, threats, vulnerability) did you identify?
 - vi) How would you have written this requirement to make sure that it is a security requirement?
- d) If the interviewee was not able to classify the requirement, the interviewer inquires about what information is missing for the classification, asking questions such as:
 - i) What additional information do you need to make the classification?
 - ii) What knowledge would you need to be able to classify the requirement?

7) When the requirements have each been discussed or there is less than 5 minutes left, the interviewer stops recording and reiterates the purpose of the recorded data and informs the interviewee about the rest of the study’s procedure (questionnaire for demographics data collection).

C. Requirements included in the interview

The requirements included in the interviews are the following:

- R-1: “The system shall deny any user to successfully use DoS (Denial-of-Service) attacks to reduce availability of the system”.
- R-2: “The door control system shall ensure that all train passengers’ doors are closed and locked when the train is running”.

- R-3: *“The system manager shall be able to define and activate the logging procedure for the critical information system.”*.
- R-4: *“When the train arrives at the station, the train control system shall open all passengers’ doors on the train driver’s request”*.
- R-5: *“The system shall log every time a user checks medications against a list of drugs noted to be ineffective for the patient in the past”*.
- R-6: *“The system shall provide reliable information to the users who have legitimate access to the website”*.
- R-7: *“The system shall register real persons as customers”*.
- R-8: *“The customer shall register to the system using a unique username and password in order to proceed to book a ticket”*.
- R-9: *“Each train passengers’ doors shall have a push button installed on the inner side to allow the passengers to open the door”*.
- R-10: *“The monitoring system shall refresh the passengers’ doors status (open/closed/locked) each second”*.

D. Closing questions

- *Do you know any method in the literature that is proposed for the elicitation of security requirements? Do you use any of these methods?*
- *What is a security requirement to you?*
- *Anything you would like to add, or any feedback on the interview you’d like to share?*